

Description of Scurvy Symptoms by John Woodall (1617)

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Location of this file: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651215>

Background

Vitamin C deficiency, scurvy, has occurred in various contexts throughout history. For example, in Nordic countries, fruit and vegetables were not available in Winter and such conditions can give rise to cases of scurvy. In addition, it is probable that during many sieges the people being surrounded did not have fresh food available and therefore started to suffer from scurvy. As an example, Olaus Magnus (1555) described symptoms consistent with scurvy in Nordic countries under sieges: “There is also another disease, the camp sickness, which distresses those who are enclosed under siege. Its symptoms are that the limbs thicken, the flesh appears to grow numb, and pus forms under the skin, so that it yields to the pressure of the fingers, like melting wax. It deadens the sensitivity of the teeth, which feel as if they will fall out, turns the colour of the skin a bluish white, and induces sluggishness together with a nausea which revolts against taking medicines” [1].

In Western countries, the harms of scurvy became particularly evident when technology enabled long voyages over oceans in sailing ships. Ships were slow, taking several weeks to reach their destination. There were no means to keep fresh foods edible for such long periods of time, and consequently most of the food available was nutritionally poor. Recent books have described scurvy from the point of view of long sea travels [2-5].

In the late 1700s, James Lind wrote a book about scurvy which is the most important book in the field of all time [6]. However, one and a half centuries earlier John Woodall (1617) wrote a book instructing ships’ surgeons for long sea voyages [7]; see biographies of Woodall [8]. Woodall’s book includes a separate chapter on scurvy, discussing symptoms, and possible causes and treatments. He describes oranges as a well-established method of treating scurvy. It has been puzzling historians that Lind did not refer to Woodall, even though Lind very extensively searched and summarized the earlier literature. In the 3rd edition of his book, Lind does mention Woodall’s book, but he does not discuss the content. Lind has often been credited for discovering oranges as a treatment for scurvy, but the benefits were known for some two centuries before Lind’s treatise.

John Woodall’s text is old English and difficult to read. In addition, it is not easily available. Though the book is currently available through the web, the text on scurvy is difficult to find in the long book. In this document we have extracted and modernized the sections that describe the symptoms of scurvy and proposals for using oranges for the treatment of scurvy. A few words remain confusing even though we used several dictionaries, and they are marked with a question mark. The original version of Woodall’s section on scurvy is available at the end of this document.

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John Woodall (1617) *The Surgion's Mate*.

Selection of sections on scurvy (p.177-202) that describe symptoms of the disease and the described benefits from oranges and lemons.

The original version of the section is copied at the end of this document.

p.177

Of the Scurvy called in Latin Scorbutum.

This lamentable disease, which has so long and so fiercely assailed sailors and seamen of all sorts more than land-men...

p.178

What the disease called the Scurvy is.

The Scurvy is a disease of the spleen, whereby is it sometimes wholly stopped, sometimes only distempered, sometimes also appearing with hard scyrros [hard tumour], swellings, beginning and showing themselves in diverse parts of the body, but more particularly on the thighs and legs, causing them to seem of a leady colour, the sharpness of which infectious humor often offends the mouths and gums of the diseased, and causes the flesh thereof to rot and stink.

p.179

The causes of the Scurvy. The names of the disease.

The Scurvy called of some *Cachexia universalis*, of other *Scletyrbe*, & of some *Stomacacen*, it is a chronic disease, not simple but compound of many other diseases.

p.180

But it is plain that this grief is a lasie [?] foule [stinking] disease with obstructions of the liver, or spleen, or of both; as also it appears that the head is much diseased, and that there is great obstructions in the brain, for that the eyes not only look evil coloured, but also the gums putrefy, and the teeth grow loose, and all the sinewy [tendon] parts of the body bear their part in the disease, for the shrinking and withering of the sinews with the great pains the party has declared no less.

p.181

Of the Scurvy or Scorbutum the signs.

The signs of the Scurvy are many, as namely, a generalized laziness and evil disposition of all the faculties and parts of the body, fauing [favouring] the stomach and the appetite which oftentimes is greater than ordinary with them along time.

A discoloring of the skin as if it were fouler than ordinary, with spots darker colored than the rest, and sometimes also darkish blue spots.

A fever at sea commonly ends in the Scurvy, wherefore by the way beware of too large purging, or phlebotomy, which increase often the grief, and make it incurable: I speak this because I have noted there is a fault in young surgeons of forwardness in taking too much blood at sea.

Also itching or aching of the limbs are signs of the grief.

Sometimes the legs falling away, and drying the calves of the legs growing hard and dry, as also immoderate swellings of the legs: also the legs and thighs discolored into freckles [freckles], or spots of a dirty brown sad color much like the color of a gangrened or mortified member.

Stinking of the breath.

Great obstructions of the liver, or spleen, or both, and in the exercising of their bodies their limbs, and their spirit failing them.

Shortness and difficulty of breathing, especially when they move themselves, but lying still finds little grief or pain.

p.182

Their eyes of a leady colour, or like dark violets.

Great swellings in the face, legs, and over all the body; paleness, or a foul pale color in the face. Swellings of the gums, rottenness of the same, with the isheving [excreting?] of much filthy blood and other stinking corruption thence, looseness of the teeth: Also some are troubled with an extreme costiveness [constipation] that for 14 days together they go not to stool once, wherefore the surgeon is constrained with an instrument to rake out the excrements to avoid death, after which extreme costiveness often follows a great flux of blood, and a painful: also many have stoppings of the urine, or at the least making less water in two days than the party drinks in one day.

A coldness and stiffness of the sinewy parts, chiefly of the legs.

Some also have their muscles, yes and sinews of their thighs, arms, and legs so wasted away that there seems to be left only the skin covering the bones.

[Dissections]

Also, it is manifest that diverse of those which have been opened after death, have had their livers utterly rotted.

Others have had their livers swollen to an exceeding greatness, some the spleen extremely swollen, others have been full of water, others their lungs putrefied and stunk whilst they have lived, these and diverse other signs too many all to be mentioned here, do afflict poor seamen, which often are past mans help, in such place and time as they happen, the cure whereof rests only in the hands of the Almighty. And yet to any man of judgment it may seem a wonder how a poor miserable man, coming on land from a long voyage even at the point of death, namely, swollen sometimes to an unreasonable greatness not able to lift a leg over a straw, nor scarce to breath by resort of strong obstruction, yet in a few days shall receive the fullness of former health, yes with little or no medicine at all.

p.184-185

Further the surgeon and his mate must not fail to persuade the governor or purser in all places where they touch in the Indies and may have it, to provide themselves of juice of Oringes, Limes, or Lemons, and at *Banthame* of Tamarinds...

And further experience teaches which I have often found true, that where a disease most rains [where a disease is most prevalent], even there God has appointed the best remedies for the same grief if it be his will they should be discovered and used: and note for substance, the Lemmons,

Limes, Tamarinds, Oringes, and other choice of good helps in the Indies which you shall find there do far exceed any that can be carried there from England...

The use of the juice of lemons is a precious medicine and well tried, being sound & good, let it have the chief place for it will deserve it...

p.191

... if the gums therefore are swollen, [so] that they hang over the teeth, stink or be putrefied...

p.192

Further if it be a swollen member ...

But if the diseases proceeds with stiffness and hardness of the sinews...

p.195

... the haemorrhage or bleeding at the nose...

p.197

The ulcers which happen to them which have this disease are many ways different from the general forms and differences of ordinary ulcers in bodies not touched with this disease, all which I have here no time to amplify. But because this disease has two general and principal differences of appearance, namely some men deceased with the Scurvy are swollen exceedingly, as in the dropsy : Others their outward limbs withered, consumed, and dried up, their sinews shrunk and grown hard, though the ulcers in the one and the other should be like in show, yet doubtless the healing of these ulcers will be found very much different, wherefore for one general note remember that the ulcers in the full and hydropsical [with edema] bodies will require more desiccative medicines...

p.198

... scurvy produces such extreme costiveness...

p. 199

Moreover, if the patient his disease be in the form of a consumption, the body being dried up as it were, or with shrinking of sinews... but if he complains much of pains in his joints...

THE
SURGIONS
MATE,

OR

A TREATISE DISCOVERING
faithfully and plainly the due
contents of the SURGIONS Chest, the uses of the
Instruments, the vertues and operations of the
Medicines, the cures of the most frequent
diseases at SEA:

Namely

Wounds, Apostumes, Vlcers, Fistulaes, Frac-
tures, Dislocations, with the true maner of Amputation,
the cure of the Scuruie, the Fluxes of the belly,
of the Collica and Illiaca Passio, Tenasmus,
and exitus Ani, the Callenture;

WITH A BRIEF EXPLANATION
of Sal, Sulphur, and Mercury; with certaine
Characters, and tearmes of Arte.

Published chiefly for the benefit of young Sea-Surgions,
imployed in the *East-India* Companies affaires.

By *John Woodall* M^r in Chirurgery.

LONDON

Printed by EDWARD GRIFFIN for *Laurence Lisle,*
at the *Tyggers-head* in *Pauls Church-yard.* 1617.

doe well to make one dressing with *Aqua vita*, wherein a stupe hot wrung out of the same, may be warme applyed to the greefe, and then warme clothes and conuenient rowlings, and sometimes also one dressing with dry lint, or of soft tow is likewise good, and sometimes *unguentum mixtum*, viz. *Basillicum & Egyptiacum ana. partes aequal.*

The defensatiue cataplasme or stufte often mentioned, is made of the ordinary restrictiue powder prescribed in the chest, mixed with the white of an egge and wine vinegar: the strongest restrictiue of all is already set downe, but in ordinary fluxes in wounds Bole may serue very well. Thus much for this time touching dismembring, being according to mine owne practise.

*The composition
of the cataplasme.*

Of the Scuruy called in Latine Scorbutum.

The Preface.

This lamentable disease, which hath so long and so Maainers most fiercely assailed Saylers and sea-men of all sorts subject to the more then Land-men. It is strange in so many Scuruy. ages past, that no one Surgeon of our country men, hath out of his experience taken in hand sincerely to set downe to posterities, the true causes, signes and cure thereof, neither left any instructions, caueats or experiences for the preuention or cure of the same, yet it may bee some may say the cure thereof is common, and wee haue in our owne countrey heere many excellent remedies generally knowne, as namely Scuruy grasse, horse reddish rootes, Nasturtia Aquaticae, Worme-wood, Sorrell, and many other good meanes, the truth

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is wee haue so, but marke how farre they extend only to the cure of those which liue at home, or else it may bee sayd, they also helpe some sea men returned from farre, who by the onely naturall disposition of the fresh aire & amendment of diet, nature her selfe in effect doth the cure without other helps, as daily it is seen.

This thing therefore being so, what should I spend my time in teaching that method, or those medicines to the Surgeons Mate, which will not bee had at sea, neither if they could bee had, will suffice for the cure therof, where the disease raigneth fiercely.

This Treatise
most concerneth
sea men.

Having therefore very small time, I must constrain my selfe to goe breefely to the businesse in hand, namely to enforme the Surgeons mate how hee should demean himselfe to comfort his patients at sea in that most dangerous disease, neither will I heere strine to giue the curious Reader other content then this, that if hee like it not, let him amend it himselfe, which I should heartily reioyce to see any good man doe, knowing mine owne weaknesse. A learned Treatise befits not my pen, and to declare those good medicines, which cannot bee had at Sea, is but time lost.

What the disease called the Scuruy is.

Definition of the
Scuruy, and the
nature thereof.

THE Scuruy is a disease of the spleene, whereby it is sometimes wholly stopped, sometimes onely distempered, sometimes also appearing with hard scyrros, swellings, beginning and shewing themselues in diuers parts of the body, but more particularly on the thighes and legges, causing them to seeme of a leady colour, the sharpnesse of which infectious humor oft offendeth the mouth and gummies of the diseased, and causeth the flesh thereof to rot and stinke.

The

The names of the disease.

THe Scuruy called of some *Caehexia uniuersalis*, of other *Sceletyrbe*, & of some *Stomacacen*, it is a chronicall disease, not simple but compound of many other diseases. *The diuers appellations thereof.*

The causes of the disease.

First the disease comes, as is sayd, by obstructions of the spleene, and by the thicknesse of the humour, not the multitude.

Some iudicious writers doe affirme this sicknesse to come by the multitude of melancholike humors gathered in *Vena Porta*, by which, it is sayd, the milt doth draw vnto it melancholly humours, and so transporteth it from the milt into the ventricle.

But truely the causes of this disease are so infinite and vnsearchable, as they farre passe my capacity to search them all out, sometimes wee finde this disease proceedeth to sea men onely, through long being at sea without touch of land, as it is seene in East India voyages, our men haue it betwixt *England*, and the *Cape de bon sperance*, as they terme it, & at their comming on land there they presently grow strong againe, & are by the very fresh ayre and fresh food cured without much other helpe. *Aire and fresh food helpeth well this disease in Sea-men.* And likewise twixt the Cape and the Indies, they are touched with it againe, and as afore sayd the fresh aire of that land, the next they come on and good diet together, cureth them with small physicall helps, and the same againe home-ward bound. The cheefe cause whereof is the contiuance of salt diet, either fish or flesh, as porke and the like, which is not to be auoyded at sea, as I suppose by the wit of man, another cause is want of sufficient nourishing food, and of sweete water; and also for want of *Aqua vita*, wine, beere, or other good water to comfort and warme their stomackes, which by contrary windes men are too much incident vnto in

long voiajes howsoeuer the Marchants are carefull, pro-
uident, and bountifull in that point.

An other cause of this disease to the ordinarie sort of
poore men, is want of fresh apparell to shift them with,
which indeed amongst poore Sailers, especially a sort of
them that are carelesse and lazie of disposition is too fre-
quent, partly also by the not keeping their apparell sweete
and dry, and the not clensing and keeping their Cabins
sweete, this also ingendreth and increaseth the infection.
Some charge Bisket as a cause of the Scuruie, but I am not
of their opinion: Some say inordinate watchings are cause
thereof: Some say extreame labour wanting due nourish-
ment: Some also affirme cares and grieffe to be some cause
thereof, others affirme the very heate of the aire, resoluing
the spirits and vapors, and ingrossing the thicke humours,
causeth the Scuruy; but what shall I amplifie further, for
it is also true that they which haue all the helps which can
be had for mony, and take as much care as men can de-
uise are euen by the euill disposition of the aire, and the
course of nature, strooke with the Scuruie, yea and die
thereof at sea and land both: yet this giueth no warrant to
the Surgeon, or his Mate to leaue their duties vnperformed,
for the blouds of those men which either by their wil-
fulnesse or slothfulnesse perish vnder their charge will sure-
ly be required at their hands.

But it is plain that this grieffe is a lasie foule disease with
obstructions of the liuer, or spleene, or of both; as also it
appeareth that the head is much diseased, and that there is
great obstructions in the braine, for that the eies not onely
looke euill coulored, but also the gummes putrifie, and
the teeth grow loose, and all the sinowie parts of the body
beare their part in the disease, for the shrinking and
withering of the sinowes with the great
paines the party hath decla-
reth no lesse.

of

Of the Scuruie or Scorbutum

• *the signes.*

THe signes of the Scuruie are many, as namely, a generall lazinesse and euill disposition of all the faculties and parts of the body, sauing the stomake and the appetite which oftentimes is greater then ordinarie with them along time.

A discoloring of the skinne as if it were fouler then ordinarie, with spots darker coulered then the rest, and sometimes also darkish blew spots.

A feuer at sea commonly ends in the Scuruie, wherfore by the way beware of too large purging, or phlebotomie, which increase oft the grieffe, and make it incurable: I speake this because I haue noted there is a fault in young Surgeons of forwardnesse in taking too much bloud at Sea.

Also itching or aking of the limmes are signes of the grieffe.

Sometimes the legges falling away, and drying the calues of the legges growing hard and drie, as also immoderate swellings of the legges: also the legges and thighes discoulered into frekells, or spots of a durty browne sad couler much like the couler of a gangrenated or mortified member.

Stinking of the breath.

Great obstructions of the liuer, or spleene, or both, and in the exercising of their bodies their limmes, and their spirit failing them.

Shortnesse and difficultie of breathing, especially when they mooue themselues, but lying still finde little grieffe or paine.

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Their eies of a leady colour, or like darke violets.

Great swellings in the face, legges, and ouer all the body; palenesse, or a foule pale couler in the face. Swellings of the gummes, rotnennesse of the same, with the isshewing of much filthy bloud and other stinking corruption thence, loosnesse of the teeth: Also some are troubled with an extreame costiuenesse that for 14 daies together they go not to stoole once, wherefore the Surgeon is constrained with an instrument to rake out the excrements to auoide death, after which extreame costiuenesse often followeth a great flux of bloud, and a painefull: also many haue stoppings of the vrine, or at the least making lesse water in two daies then the party drinketh in one day.

A coldnesse and stifnesse of the sinowy parts, chiefly of the legges.

Some also haue their muskells, yea and sinowes of their thighes, armes, and legges so wasted away that there seemeth to be left only the skinne couering the bones.

*Certaine signes
of the Scuruie by
the dead opened &
discovered.*

Also it is manifest that diuers of those which haue been opened after death, haue had their liuers vtterly rotted.

Others haue had their liuers swolne to an exceeding greatnesse, some the spleene extreamely swolne, others haue bene full of water, others their lungs putrified and stunke whilst they haue liued, these and diuers other signes too many all to be mentioned here, doe afflict poore seamen, which often are past mans helpe, in such place and time as they happen, the cure whereof resteth only in the hands of the Almighty. And yet to any man of iudgement it may seeme a wonder how a poore miserable man, comming on land from a long voiage euen at the point of death, namely, swolne sometimes to an vnreasonable greatnesse not able to lift a legge ouer a straw, nor scarce to breath by reason of strong obstruction, yet in a few daies shall receiue the fulnesse of former health, yea with little or no medicine at all.

The cure of this disease, as a famous writer named *Iohannes Echthius* in a treatise *de scorbuto* affirmeth, consisteth chiefly

chiefly in foure things, namely in opening obstructions, euacuating the offending humors, in altering the property of them, and in comforting and corroborating the parts late diseased.

Iohannes Vicrius another famous writer ascribeth the whole cure of the Scurvie to the herbe Spooone worte. One *Olaus Magnus* a Swedon writer, in his fifteenth booke, and fiftie one Chapter, intreating of this grieffe attributerh the whole cure therof to be in *Absinthio* or worm-wood, namely, to drinke much of the infusion thereof, and also of the salt of the same: and one chiefe part of the cure of the Scurvie (saith he) consists in good diet, but the sea-men are inioyned to that onely the Ship affordeth, which the better and sounder their prouisions of victualls are, the more their men stand in health; and the contrarie not onely bringeth many diseases, but maketh the diseases which happen very hard to be cured, therefore I may spare labour in writing what broths or herbs serue best where no fresh foode can be gotten: the Surgeon and his Mate must therefore, seeing he is at sea deprived of one principall help in that cure, namely, fresh meat and good drinke, be diligent to call for such comfortable things as are by the great care and bountie of the Marchants provided for sick men, or those which incline thereunto, whereof in each Shippe is a good proportion both of wine, sugar, spices and other comfortable things, and to see they haue it in due measure: and likewise to complaine to the Gouvernours if they be withheld from the same, or if any man abuse himselfe by misse diet: yea and oftentimes, namely morning and euening to seeke for weake and poore men in their Cabins, or so soone as they are missing at their messes to inquire for them, and to see their Cabins be sweet, and their prouisions according, or to moue and intreat the Master, or Gouvernour of the Shippe for redresse in such cases, for feare of a generall infection. And whereas the first part of this cure is in the opening of obstructions, it is therefore fit in the beginning of the grieffe to giue a leni-
tiue.

Remedies touch-
ing the Scurvie.

The Surgeons
dutie in this
disease at sea.

riue glister, then the next day if the party be strong open a veine, but beware, as is said, of taking too much bloud away at once, especially where the liuer is weake or stopped, and wheremen want good nutriment, for many euills ensue thereby, The next day following his bleeding if he can beare it, and if that his disease be with a swelling or fulneise, giue him a doise of the pills of Euphorbium or otherwise of pipularaffi, or of Cambogia, and make him some comfortable spoone meate, such as you can make at sea; namely, an oatmeale caudell would not bee a misse of a little beere or wine, with the yolke of an egge, and a little sugar made warme and giuen him to drinke, or any comfortable broath made with currants and other fruite, or spices moderately taken, or with sugar, or as the shippe can afford, a barley water for his ordinary drinke were not amisse, with some few drops of Cinamon water therein, and also some iuice or sirupe of lemons therein, or a few drops of oyle of vitriole and some sugar, and giue him in his drinke by way of infusion, dried wormewood good store for it is very wholesome.

Further the Surgeon and his Mate must not faile to perswadethe Gouvernor or Purser in all places where they touch in the Indies and may haue it, to provide themselves of iuice of Oringes, limes, or Lemons, and at *Ban-thame* of Tamarinds: Also sometime though a man bee well, a comfortable caudell made with some wine, spices, sugar, and the yolke of an egge were very good; for these are helps in that case as well to prevent the disease, as also to helpe it when it comes.

*The excellencie
of the Iuice of
Lemons, Limes,
Oringes, and
Tamarinds.*

And further experience teacheth which I haue oft found true, that where a disease most raineth, euen there God hath appointed the best remedies for the same greefe if it be his will they should be discovered and vsed: and note for substance, the Lemmons, Limes, Tamarinds, Oringes, and other choyce of good helps in the Indies which you shall finde there doe farre exceed any that can be carried thither from England, and yet there is a good quantity of
Iuice

Iuice of Lemmons sent in each ship out of England by the great care of the Marchants, and intended onely for the releefe of euery poore man in his neede, which is an admirable comfort to poore men in that disease: also I find we haue many good things that heale the Scuruy well at land, but the Sea Surgeon shall doe little good at Sea with them, neyther will they indure. The vse of the iuice of Lemons is a precious medicine and wel tried, being sound & good, let it haue the chiefe place for it will deserue it, the vse whereof is: It is to be taken each morning, two or three spoonfuls, and fast after it two houres, and if you adde one spoonefull of *Aquavita* thereto to a cold stomacke, it is the better. Also if you take a little thereof at night it is good to mixe therewith some suger, or to take of the syrups thereof is not amisse. Further note it is good to be put into each purge you giue in that disease. Some Surgeons also giue of this iuice daily to the men in health as a preseruatue, which course is good if they haue store, otherwise it were best to keepe it for neede. I dare not write how good a sauce it is at meat, least the chiefe in the ships waste it in the great Cabins to saue vinegar. In want whereof vse the iuice of Limes, Oringes, or Citrons, or the pulpe of Tamarinds: and in want of all these vse oyle of Vitrioll as many drops as may make a cup of beere, water or rather wine if it may be had, onely a very little as it were sower, to which you may also adde suger if you please, or some sirups, according to your store and the necessity of that disease, for of my experience I can affirme that good oyle of Vitrioll is an especiall good medicine in the cure of the Scuruy, as also in many other greefes, the which in another place is noted. Further a decoction of Branne and therein Almonds ground, adding Cinamon and Rosewater a little, and some Suger were very comfortable now and then to be taken to refresh the stomacke. And as touching the Tamarinds brought from the Indies they are to be eaten of themselues as the substance of them is, namely to eat them as you would prunes, and being made into con-

*The Marchants
care for Seamen*

*Land medicines
for the Scuruy,
bad Sea medi-
cines.*

*The iuice of
Lemmons a good
preseruatine.*

B b

serues

*Tamarinds must
be vsed sparingly
if a fluxe be fea-
red.
Elect. Diatrion-
piperion.*

serues, eat them as other Conferues on the point of a knife sucking out the substance, and putting forth the stalkes or stoncs thereof, some dissolue them in wine or water, and worke out the substance of them therein, and cast away the rest taking onely that which is pure: one may vse this medicine so oft as ye please without danger or harme, onely if hee feare a fluxe of the belly, or haue a weakenes in the raines, let him not eat too much of the Tamarinds. Also the Electuary *Diatrionpiperion* giuen each morning a little on the point of a knife fasting, and last, namely at the party his going to bed, is a great preseruatiue; for it doth warme and coroborate the stomacke, and preserueth from the Scuruy, and is very comfortable to bee giuen to any one that is diseased with the same, or subiect thereto. And the *Theriaca Diatefferon* is yet better, for it hath an especial vertue in curing that disease. Also *Venice Treacle*, *Mithridate*, and *London Treacle* preserue well from this disease daily taken fasting, and so doth conferue of Roses and Berberies mixed with a little oyle of Vitriole, and giuen on the point of a knife.

Greene Ginger is also very good to comfort the stomacke, and so are all sorts of *Myrabolans* Condite, and also all sorts of strong Cordiall waters, but chiefly good *Rosafolis* and good wormwood water, yea and very good *Aquavita* helpeth well, Currants and Keysons of the Sun are likewise very good.

Also all kinds of Spices moderately taken are good, and so is good wine a very good preseruer of the body from this disease, with also the continuance of fresh diet, which is hard to bee gotten at sea, the excelsse of which good things is as dangerous.

The principall Laxatiue medicine which I would aduise in this case is pills of *Euphorbium* wherewith the body being swolne and watery, you may at your pleasure make euacuation thereof: these purge also by vrine very well the dosse being ℥ss, or at the most ℥ij. These are the fitter for that disease, because they purge not alone water, but also

also by their great warmth, they comfort and warme the stomacke and intralls.

These I aduise the Surgeons mate to vse, as is said, where the body aboundeth with ouer much cold and crude humidity, but let your dosse alwaies respect the strength of the patient, for any strong purging is not good in the Scuruy: all sodaine and strong euacuations are to be auoided. Also *Aquilla Laxatiue* is a very good purge in this case, namely eight or ten graines thereof taken in a cup of wine. It cureth also all wormes of the body, and killeth them wheresoeuer they be. But if the stomacke onely bee oppressed with the greefe in this disease, I first giue a dose of pills called *Pilule Ruffi*, namely ʒ.ij: you shall finde them to be very good.

Note further, that if any dose or the whole masse of pils in the Chest, such time as you would administer them be growne too hard, then you may dissolue them with any sirup you haue, or with good honey a very little, namely one onely drop will serue to dissolue one dose at once if the masse prooue too liquid, you may roule it in some of the *Puluis Arthreticus* till it be hard enough. Also the moderate vse of Veriuce, Vineger, or Oximell hath beene found very good in this case.

Furthermore, if you see cause, certaine daies after you haue giuen of any your former Laxatiues, you may giue a sweat to the patient in his bed, namely you may giue him a scruple of *Mithridate*, *Venice Treakle*, or *London Treakle* or *Diatefferon*, and mixe therewith if you haue it eight or ten graines of the *Diaphoretice*, and being but ordinarily couered, he shall sweat sufficiently if he stirre not too much. Also the sweating in moist baths I confesse to be good medicines in this case, though not well to be performed at Sea for the ordinary men. And whereas one accident dangerous in this disease is extreme Costiuenesse as is mentioned, with also stopping of Vrine: the remedies for the Costiuenes, is first that you attempt to mooue the belly by a lenitiue glister as is said, made rather of a slimy decocti-

How to make a
glisters in case of
necessity for the
Scurvie.

A speciall ob-
servation in gi-
uing these afore
said glisters.

on or medicine which might leaue no sharpe Astringent or desiccative quality behind it, yea though it purge not much, for the sharp Purgers after their working cause often a more Costiuenes then was before, or by their violence cause a weakenes in the stomacke and intrals, whence followeth a fluxe, wherefore for glisters at Sea in great Costiuenesse, where the Apothecaries shop and Cheap-side is not at hand, make a slimy decoction of *Althea* rootes or Comfery rootes, or in want thereof, of Linseeds & Fenogreeke bruised, of each ℥ss: in want thereof, of Bran ℥ij. to the decoction being strained, adde of *species Hiera Pigra* ℥ij of salt halfe a spoonfull, of honey as much, of oyle two spoonfulls: all these put together, let the decoction mentioned be so fitted that all may be but one wine pint, and administer it with the Siring, beeing of a iust temper in warmth, but if you intend not to haue it purge much, leaue out the *species hiera pigra*, and it will giue 2, or 3. stooles. You may for an ordinary glisters well also take one quart of the broth from the beefe kettle, adding thereto of linseed ℥ij, comfry rootes and March mallow rootes if they may be had, a small quantity of Aniseed and fennell seed, ana ℥ij, boyle these halfe an houre, then adde honey and common oyle of each a spoonefull, & giue one wine pint of this for a glisters: but if you see it worke not but come away without excrement, the former recited will doe well, or make an other stronger, namely *ad colaquintida* ℥ij, in the beginning of the decoction to the aforesaid decoction, provided there be no inflammation in *Longauū*, or *intestinū rectum*, nor any excoriation, which by the patient his complaint is knowne: this decoction being boyled and ready to be administred, you may yet adde of the *species Hiera* ℥2 thereto, or of the *Puluis Arthreticus* ℥j. rather, for it inflameth not, it were best in my opinion to striue in this disease by glisters to giue but one or two stooles at one time, for sharpe glisters offend much. Therefore though I shew what you may doe, yet be well aduised in doing of it. Also of pills of *Euphorbium*, haue a care you giue them
not

not where there is an inflammation or inward heate in the guts, in such a case, the *Aquilla Laxativa* will be a better medicine, which will both temper the inward heate and help to heale the interalls, and yet wil purge him well, and doth not binde him againe presently, and prouoketh also vrine very well, for *Aquilla Laxativa* will often cause naturall loosenes, certaine daies after the taking thereof, and will purge water very much both by stoole and vrine: and because as is said, extreme costiuenes is great hurt to the body, the Surgeon must by his best care to the patient, seeke to preuent it, both by teaching him to doe his best for his owne health, & to amend the same by obseruing good customes and diet: by customes, namely that hee faile not daily, once a day at the least to offer himselfe to stoole, and doe his best to vrge some excrement to come, and somewhat to force his body thereunto if occasion be, and to keepe one and the same hower daily as neere as hee can: I know by prooffe it helpeth much, and for diet to vse also as neere as he can those things which hee findeth procure an inward slipperinesse and loosenesse in the guts, pease, oatmeale, and rice doe somewhat thereunto, provided they be very well boiled, and the adding currants thereto is the better, and oyle and butter are good helpes, but at land where it may be had, all kindes of fresh diet almost are good in that case, for by the leauing onely Sea diet, the body refresheth it selfe sodainly through benefit of nature and the fresh aire, and easily becommeth naturally loose, and then the difficulty is ended. The eating of Tamarinds is likewise a good thing in that case.

For heate in the Intestines vse Aquila Laxativa.

A caution.

The third rule ceaseth, the Mariners on shore.

What I haue written here plainly, touching meane and simple glifters; I would not be mistaken, as if I did it out of ignorance or disdaine of better medicines, for I were worse then foolish if I would reiect, detract or disswade from the good vse of decoctions of hearbes, feedes, &c. with the additions of Eleſtuaries, Laxatiue Sirupes and the like which I haue in daily vse at home vpon each iust occasion: yet many of the ancient Artists of worthy me-

Bb3

mory

mory which I could rehearse, haue in former ages vsed for glisters only water and salt with oyle, and some others haue added honey, and it is manifest that new milke alone is a good comfortable glister with the yolke of an egge, and a little course sugar added.

And you may also many times saue a labor of giuing a glister by a suppository, which is either to be made of a long peece of Allum scraped smooth, or of a candles end, or of a peece of hard sope, or of honey and salt sodden till it bee so hard that it will breake being colde, which being yet hot may be rowled & made vp of the greatnesse of a finger, & administred: of any of these, I say, you may make a suppository as long and bigge as a finger or lesse, and thrust it vp into *Ano*, & let the party keep this medicine one houre at the least in his body (if he possibly can.) Further note this generall rule concerning Glisters, let a Glister neuer ex-

The quantity of a glister to be regarded.

The true temper of the glister to be administred.

How to deliuer a glister if the Longanum bee stopped.

A glister for inflammation and excoriation in the guts.

ceede the quantity of one wine pint, let it rather want one quarter, especially when you giue it to a costieue body, or a ful body, he shal be much the abler & the willingler to keep it the iust time. Further beware it be not too hot nor too colde, for the guts are tender parts, so hot as pitse new made, or a very little rather warmer is the true temper. But if you perceiue the *Intestinum rectum* or Arse-gut, to bee excoriated or inflamed, in such a case vse no salt nor salt broathes, nor strong Laxatiues, as *Euphorbium*, *Agaricum*, *Hiera Pigra*, *Coloquintida*, or the like. If you find the *Longanum* or Arse-gut to be clung, or hard stopped with excrement, you may put a smal greasie or oily clout on the end of your glister-pipe only ouer the holes therof, when you put it into the body, and thrust it into the head of the pipe then draw backe a little your hand and deliuer in your medicine, and if you see cause, and that it will not easily deliuer, force it somewhat. Also when your medicine is all in, and that you would draw out your instrument againe, doe it quickly, and let the party turne him on his backe, and he shall keepe the medicine in the better. In cases of excoriations or inflammations of the intrailles, in Glisters vse

Deere

Deere fuet ℥ij. for one glister, and in want thereof, *Axungia ouina vel porcina*, I meane sheep or swines fat, and let the decoction whereof the glister is made, be onely of branne, and without any other addition, and giuen now and then such a glister, I meane once a day, for two or three daies, after you may add thereto some small astringent medicines, as *Succus Acatia* ℥j. or Gales ℥-ij. or Balustians ℥β. or Myrabolans, ℥-iij. euen as you see cause, for these helpe to heale the guts well.

Of Lotions.

Concerning Lotions to the mouth and throat of the diseased, they must be sharpe and very astringent, I meane them especially which concerne the cure of the gummies in the Scurvie, if the gummies therfore be swolne, that they hang ouer the teeth, stinke or be putrified, they must be very well lanced or scarified, and after hard rubbed with a linnen or wollen cloth, wrapped about the fore finger and wet in some strong restringent or Stiptick Lotion very hot, as is the ordinarie Lotion of Allum, Honey and Hearbes, adding thereto a double quantitie of Allum, and a little salt peeter, or gun-powder for a neede is good, & if it be not sufficiently strong, make a stronger decoction of coperas in water, adding salt peeter with a little honey, if you haue it, or *Mell Rosarum*, with also a little strong vineger, you may also put oile of Vitrioll a little thereto, but that it hath one euill qualitie in hurting and softning the teeth, wherefore beware of it, and if you vse it, do but onely touch the gummies with it oncé and no more, and it will doe much good: and if you please, also *Aqua Fallopij* is good, but because it is made with sublimed Mercurie, it is not without danger, and is also of a loathsome taste and smell, and offendeth the stomacke very much, but I know it to be held by many for a great secret, but as for my selfe for reasons rehearsed, I vse it not but aduise rather that which is strong eyther of the Coperas, Allome, or Salt-peeter, for

The cure of the gums much swolne, stinking and putrified.

for they hurt not the teeth at all as doth the oyle of Vi-
trioll, and so doth *Aqua fortis* very much, or you may
make a Lotion thus: R̄ Coperas, white, greene or blew ℥ij.
water one pound or thereabout, Honey one spoonefull,
boyle these to the consumption of one third or halfe, then
take of *Lapis Medicamentofus*, or salt-peeter ℥is, and if you
haue no honey, take Suger, or iuice of Licorice, or Lico-
rice boyled therein for to make it pleasant in taste, or with-
out for a need you may vse it, or the *Lapis Medicamentofus*
dissolued into faire water, maketh an excellent Lotion for
the putrified gums.

Outward reme-
dies for the
Scuruy in gene-
rall.

If swelling
grow in any
part a Lixiuum
is good.
Of what the
Lixiuum is
made.

Touching good outward remedies for the cure of this
greefe, bathes, fomentations, with also good oyles, vn-
guents, cerotes, cataplasmes, or emplasters, are each ne-
cessary in their due times, prouided they be of comforta-
ble ingredients, namely those which minister warmth and
nourishment to the diseased parts, and open the pores ob-
structed, all such, I say, are most fit, prouided they bee al-
waies applyed very warme, and the party belayd and kept
warme vpon it. Further if it bee a swolne member, then
this following bathe to foment the member, will bee
good, namely a *Lixiuum* made of fresh water and a-
shes, and being onely but reasonable sharpe, (for too sharp
of the ashes, will ouer heat, yea & excoriate) this done and
cleered, boile some hot hearbes, flowers and seedes fitting
therein, such are Camomile, Mellilote, Dill, Worme-
wood, Balme, Rosemary, Time, Sage, Bay-leaues, Bay-
berries, Iuniper berries, Anis-seede, Fennell, Coriander,
Carraway, Dill seedes, or the the like: these ingredients, or
those of them which may be had, and let them be boyled
a little therein. and either stupes of woollen or linnen clo-
thes wet therein or put the ingredients into bagges after
the decoction is made with them, and the place well fo-
mented therewith, and so laid to sweat with some of the
hearbes in the same bagges well wrung out and hot appli-
ed, till the next dressing. But if the disease proceede with
stiffenelle and hardnesse of the sinewes, then forbear the
Lixiuum,

Lixiuum, I meane put no ashes thereto, and make the decoction of the mentioned ingredients, boyled in the broath of the beefe-kettle, in wine, beere, or water for a neede, adding some salt, and likewise, if you haue it, Linseed oyle, neats-foot oile, sheepes-foot oile, or oile of almonds, oyle of chamomile, Dill or earth-wormes, of Bayes, of Lillies or some one of them.

Also where you can haue it, a good bathe of the blood of beasts, either coves, horses, asses, goats, or sheeps blood is exceeding good, namely, to put the legges of the patient, yea and his body too, if it may bee, into a tub made fitting, and the blood kept warme, part thereof being still kept hot on the fire, and renew therewith the bath still, as it coolerth with the warme blood, for some reasonable time, this restoreth and comforteth mightily the decayed spirits. Milke of it selfe is also good to be vsed in that kind where it may be had.

A bath of blood very good.

The manner how to bathe in this bath of blood.

A bath of milke.

Of Oyles thereto.

Oyles good to annoynt, which are *Oleum Chamamilla, Laurini. Anethi* or *Lumbricorum*, with a little Spike oyle, oyle of Turpentine, oyle of Nutmegs pressed out, oyle of Peeter, oyle of Exitor or oyle of Iuniper, or one of the same mixed with them, or some good *Aquavita*, & to vse strong frication with warme soft hands long continued, helpeth much.

Oyles good outward helps and what they be.

Much and hard frication very beneficiall.

Vnguents.

Good Vnguents to help these greefes, in my opinion, are euery warme and comforting Vnguent in vse in the Surgeons chest, but I haue had especiall triall of an Vnguent, the composition whereof shall be heereafter described, which is named *Contra Scorbutum*, as also of the *Vnguentum Populeon*, I meane the same composition *Valerius Cordus* hath described, for I finde it to bee very good:

What Vnguents are heerein helpfull.

Two principall Vnguents of so ueraigne vertue against the Scuruy.

Cc

but uy.

but you may well say, how doth hee contradict himselfe, which euen now aduiseeth warming Vngueats, and presently reciterh *Populeon* for one, which is knowen to bee colde, but though I haue haste, let mee I pray thee answer for my selfe in that one poynt, which I know to be a principall *Arcanum* in healing not looked vnto: many a medicine hath a seeming shew to be colde, & yet doth contrary effects, witnesse Quicksiluer, Iuyce of Lemmons, Vitrioll, oyle of Vitrioll, Salt peeter, Allum, Sorrell, and diuers others which I could recite, all which may easily bee prooued, either hot or colde, by their seuerall strong operations and effects which they performe: as for example, to begin with Quicksiluer, it is affirmed to be extreame cold of infinite writers, and his repercussive quality sheweth the same as also in repelling and cooling hot tumors: with also the variety of colde diseases and contractions Podagricall and Chyrurgicall, procured therby to diuers artificers which worke much therewith, as namely to guilders, Foilers of looking-glasses, and the like Tradef-men, which sheweth the same to be cold. It also sheweth it selfe to bee hot diuersly, as namely in that it is so extreame subtill and penetratiue, so inuisible to enter the body (*per poros cutis*) and being in the body, so volatill and busie, so causticke & corrosiue, so extreame Laxatiue, so diaphoreticke, so diueriticke, so mundificatiue, so incarnatiue and so sigillatiue or siccatrizing, as the like medicine by the art or wit of man was neuer found out: iuyce of Lemmons was euer reputed a colde medicine, prescribed and giuen dayly by the Physicians in burning and pestilentiall feouours, and that with great reason, and good successe euen to this day, and yet to that notable, and colde, and terrible disease of the Scuruy, how excellent hath it been approued, how then in these two recited medicines holds the old Axiome *Similia conseruantur similibus & contraria contrariorum remedia sunt*? euen as true as *vox populi vox dei*, pepper is hot in the mouth and cold in the mawe; if I would desire truely to coole and temper the boyling
of

Many medicines in shew that which in effect are not.

What Quicksiluer is in shew and in effect.

The different vertue of the iuyce of lemons.

of the bloud inwardly, which I my selfe would take, yea were it vpon the safegard of my owne life I would take five or sixe drops of good oyle of Vitrioll in a draught of faire water with a little sugar, a drop or two of Rose-water and as much wine vineger, marke well my words if thou knowest not these medicines they are worth knowing, or $\text{ʒ} \text{ j}$ of pepper, salt niter, which is also called *Lapis prunella*, in the like liquor, and for want of the sugar, rose-water, or vineger of it selfe, or with the water only for a neede: I haue often prooued them so true coolers that they haue staied the Hemoragie or bleeding at the nose; the latter whereof shall seldome faile if you by outward meanes proceede rationally by applying to the forehead cold and astringent things, as also to the nape of the neck: also a large spung wet in cold water and applied to his secret parts is good, or let him hold or put his members into a boule of cold water, also binding hard the armes and legges is very good to stay bleeding at the nose; and one of the surest remedies but last to be attempted in Hemoragie or bleeding at the nose, is to open a veine in the arme on the same side. Thus it may plainly appeare that two of the recited medicines are cold: now to proue those two hot, I will not spend many words, call to minde that of Vitrioll and Salt-peeter *Aqua fortis* is made, which by his heate and penetrating force, teareth to peeces and dissolueth the strongest mettalls presently, deuoureth & vnterly destroyeth cloths woollen and linnen, or put but good oyle of Vitrioll into an vlcer, or to the whole skin and tell me halfe an houre after what a cold feur the Patient had: or put fire to crude salt niter alone and marke the conclusion, namely it will prooue it selfe wholly combustible, and therefore hot: as I suppose likewise the herbe Sorrell, it is a cold herbe esteemed at least in the first if not in the second degree, and yet consider well if you seeke quickly to ripen and bring to suppuration an Apostume you shall finde it a most excellent speedy remedie: I conceiue therefore that it is not by his coldnesse it doth that effect

A singular and approved good medicine to temper the boiling of bloud.

To stop bleeding at nose good rules.

What opposite vertues Vitriol, Salt-peter, and aqua fortis haue.

The like in Salt Nitro.

As also like different operation in Sorrell.

A Saying of
Oswaldus Cro-
bius.

fect, for that is not common nor rationally, and therefore to conclude my degression as *Ozwardus Crollius* a late learned writer saith in his Preface Admonitorie to his booke called *Bazilla Chimica Simplicium: qualitates non semper consideranda sed earum arcana*, The simple and apparant qualities of Medicines are not alwaies alone to be respected, but rather their mysteries or hidden vertues.

Gods prouidence
to be obserued in
Physickes opera-
tion.

Thus much in defence of the temperament of some priuate Medicines working strange and feuerall effects, wherein the mysteries of our God in his diuine prouidence farre do excell whatsoeuer things else, shewing mans wisdom meere foolishnesse, wherefore to him for euermore be praise, Amen.

Where the vngu-
ents are to be
applied.

The warme vnguents are to be vsed where you see apparant neede by reason of the coldnesse of the part, the Populeon wherethere is paine though no manifest signe of a hot disease appeare, and doubtlesse it will worke good effect to your comfort, yea though you thinke the disease be not cold, and therefore neede a more warming Medicine, *Unguentum Dialthea* is one of the best vnguents, and *Martiatum* is another, *Oleum Laurini* is also good, and if you list to adde some more califying oyles, take of oyle of Speeke, of Terbinthine, or Petreolum, but good warme application and strong frication is the meane, and warme keeping. Of medicines to be applied to the Spleene, Liuer, or stomake outwardly, the vnguent *pectorale* described is very good. warme to annoint those parts, whose description with the rest you shall finde, and to lay also ouer the whole part agriued the *Emplastrum mellilote pro splene*, whose description is expressed in the Dispensatory, for want of which Plaster *Emplastrum cumini* is good. Also the well annointing with oyle of Nutmegges, or Mace adding a few drops of oyle of Cloues Chymicall doth much comfort, keeping the griued part extraordinary warme.

What outward
medicines the
liuer and sto-
make require.

of

*Of Ulcers in those that haue
the Scuruie.*

THe Ulcers which happen to them which haue this disease are many waies different from the generall formes and differences of ordinary Vlcers in bodies not touched with this disease, all which I haue here no time to amplifie. But because this disease hath two generall and principall differences of appearance, namely some men deceased with the Scuruie are swollen exceedingly, as in the drop sic: Others their outward limmes with red, consumed, and dried vp, their sinowes shrunke and growne hard, though the Vlcers in the one and the other should be like in shew, yet doubtlesse the healing of these Vlcers will be found very much different, wherefore for one generall note remember that the Vlcers in the full and hydropticall bodies will require more desiccatiue medicines, as namely the *Vnguentum diapompholigos, de minio, Vnguentum album Camphoratum* and the like: And the other kind the *Vnguentum basilicon incarnatiuum*, and the *Arceus* linament and the like to those. Some sea Surgeons haue commended to me of their practise the vse of *Vesicatory* medicines, namely *Contharides* in painfull swolne limmes, which I leaue to the practise of others further to commend the same, my selfe hauing referued it as a great secret from a Surgeon my friend, but made no such experiences thereof my selfe.

And further touching the cure of Vlcers in this disease vntil the obstructions of the liuer and spleene be removed, those Vlcers giue no place to good healing; wherefore since notwithstanding they must bee carefully attended for conscience sake, I aduise that all sharpe and violent medicines be shunned, and all soft and anodinethings

Cc 3

applied

Two strange effects the Scuruie causeth, the first an Hydropticall inflation of the whole body.

A second is consumption of the body.

Experience the best praifer.

Obstructions of the Liuer must be removed before the Vlcers can be cured.

A caut.

applied that you know or can learne, provided they bee warrantable medicines, for otherwise they not only strue against a streame, but put your Patient to needleffe disquiet, and thereby increase this disease.

How to help the body extremely bound through the Scurvy.

I haue here in part shewed the Surgeons mate my opinion concerning the cure of the Scuruie, to which hee may ioyne his owne and other mens experience, where he can gaine instructions worth following, together with his owne daily practise, which, if he be wise, he may likewise set downe, onely let me aduise the young practitioner that sometimes (as my selfe haue experienced) the scuruie produceth such extreame costiuenesse, as neither *suppositorie*, glister, or any Laxatiue medicine whatsoeuer will auaille, but that the excrements must be drawne out of the *Longanum*, or the *Intestinum rectum* with an instrument, for they will be like drie lumps of clay, or hard sheepes trecles, as they terme them, the which instrument I haue appointed and is an easie and a fit instrument, called by me *Spathula Munda*, which instrument being a little warmed, is then to be annointed with oyle, and so gently put into *Ano* to draw out the excrements, and to make way for the glister-pipe, which, when it hath clenfed some sixe inches, or fve inches, you may assay by a glister againe. Furthermore it sometime happeneth, that by the long remaining of the excrements in the *Longanum*, the gut is either excoriated, or at the least inflamed. In such a case you may take notice that you forbear salt, as is said, and ail sharpe heating things in your glisters, as *Coloquintida*, *Hierapigra*, *Scamony*, *Agaricum*, *Euphorbium*, and the like: and content your selfe to administer for the first, a glister made onelie of a decoction of Bran alone, or of Mallowes, or of Comfry rootes small cut, or Linseeds bruised with ζij of Deere suet, *Vnguentum Diapompholigos*, or as much *populeon* or *Vnguentum album*, as is said, and rather if you finde that helpe not, giue a dose of *Aquilla Laxativa* which will purge easily without any offence at all, and helpe to heale the gut, and this course is better then by sharpe glisters to
purge

What must be done for the cure thereof.
A glister.

Aquilla Laxativa.

purge, which will offend the gut, and after the said purge it will not be amisse if you see occasion, to giue a like glister againe as before, and note that if in the glister some of the ingredients should be wanting, you may neuer the lesse proceed with the rest with good profit, provided if you haue better you vse them, neither doe I heere intend strictly to enioyne the Surgeons mate to my rule, but if hee haue better, let him vse it, and forget mine in the name of God.

The aforesaid glister repeated.

Moreouer, if the patient his disease be in the forme of a consumption, the body being dried vp as it were, or with shrinking of the sinewes: then if you intend to purge the party, giue him pills called *Pilula Rassi* for the first remedie, but if he complain much of paines in his ioynts, then a dole of *Puluis Arthreticus* will do best, or purge him with *Aquila Laxatiua*, it is also a general good purge at al times, and almost in all cases, though best in the French Pox and Dropsie. And though I haue formerly touched the forms of some Cataplasmes, yet for that there hath bene much good found in the application of this Cataplasme made being of warming, comforting and anodine medicines, I thought good to note it, which is as followeth. R the flowers of Cammomile, Mellilot flowers, Wormwood & Hipericon and Balme, of each M. j, Bran M. j. ij, Linseed, Fenigreeke, of each ℥ss. Comfrey and Mallow roots, of each ℥ss, barley meale ℥ij. bruise the herbs, and boyle these in milke, beere, or water, then adde of oyle of Camomile, Dialthæ, oyle of Dill, of each ℥ij, *Axungia* ℥iiij, apply it warme: note likewise, that where you haue not all these recited ingredients, yet that you take so many of them as you haue, and try their force, for if a few will do the business, as sometimes it will, it were vaine & wast to vse many.

The cure if the body be consumed by the Scurvie.

Wherein the chiefest vertue of Aquilla Laxatiua consists.

Cataplasmes excellent in this case. How to make the Cataplasme.

Sometimes for a need you may make good vse of a decoction of Bisket in wine or beere, which warme applied will wonderfully comfort a weake limme, and allwage the paine, for sometimes the very good warmth with good ligature auaieth much: fatty things must bee forborne in some,

*Some things
better than fat
in this disease.*

some cases, namely when the paine is sharpe and quicke, least you cause putrifaction & suppuration of humours against your will, yea and rather vse Acetosous medicines, and Anodine sometime, also muslage medicines are to be forborne, for like reasons: in all which cases, confer with other writers: aske counsell of thy Elders, and keepe euer in writing thy owne good obseruations from time to time.

Counsell directing what to be done if means may be had.

A word or two to conclude for the young Surgeons concerning the cure of this disease, when they come vpon a coast where you may haue some helps, let them vse some one of these following, they shall find them good vpon triall.

Rx: Absuthia, Iuniper Berries of each m. j, Goats milke, lib. 4, boyle this together, the hearbs and berries well bruised till a third part be consumed, then straine it, and adde of saffron in powder ζ -j, stirre it on the fire till it haue boyled a very little, and set it to cleer, and giue the sicke thereof three times a day at the least, viz. morning, noone, and night, this drinke hath cured many in great distresse: if you haue no goates milke, sheeps milke, or for a need, Cowes milke will serue.

Another.

*Another good
drinke.*

Rx. Water Cresses, Sorrell, and Wormewood, of each one handfull; bruise them well, and broyle them in three quarts of Whey or new milke, and adde thereto a little suger and saffron, and let the sicke drinke thereof as often as hee will.

*Whey sodden
with diuers
hearbs very
profitable.*

Whay drunken of it selfe is very good, but better if, the iuices of scuruy grasse, sorrell, Coclaria, wormewood, Watercresses, the greater or lesser sort, Brooklime, Scordium, Spoonewort, water Iermander, or of some of them be mixed therewith, for that they are all approoued good medicines, and doubtlesse some of them are to be found in other Countries and coasts, as well as in England.

Also

Also an infusion or gentle decoction of the roots of the hearbe *Rhaphane fistulosus*, or horse-reddish in vineger, or mixed with beere and drunke, is exceeding good, or eaten of it selfe with bread. ¶

Bay berries, and Iuniper berries are also wholsome boyled in whay against this disease, for they open obstructions: likewise from these former hearbs may many other good compound medicines be made. *Bay-berries also and Iuniper-berries are good.*

And generally note, that bitter and sower medicines preuaile most to the cure of this greefe, amongst which sower medicines you haue that are approued good there-to, these that follow as cheefe, Iuice of Lemons, of Limes, Citrons, and Oringes. *Sowre medicines very good.*

Oyle of Vitrioll, oyle of Sulphur, spirit of Salt, vineger of Wine, and the spirit thereof: also the Sirups thereof, so many as are in vse, and the rather, for that they cut away the tough and grosse flegme, and haue power also to open obstructions. In like manner, the iuice or pulpe of Tamarinds hath a great acetosity, and is found a precious remedy against this disease, the vse whereof is noted already.

Also: note further that there are few diseases at sea happening to Sea-men, but the Scuruy hath a part in them, the fluxes which happen chiefly proceed from the Scuruy, and I suppose if Seamen may be preferued from that disease, few other diseases would indanger them. *An obseruation.*

The conclusion.

THESE recited medicines for Christian charity I thought not amitte to publish, admonishing young men to be wise and carefull to make right vse of them, and as neere as they can, to respect in the vse thereof, Time, Place, Age, quantity, quality, temperament, strength, climate, cause, and what else is fitting to be regarded for the good of the sicke, and credit of themselues, and let them auoide slothfulness, auarice, enuy, feare, pride, or what else may hinder these

D d

these

these duties, that God may giue a blessing to their labours and then the praise and comfort shall returne to themselves, which God grant.

And for the elder sort of graue Artifts, I craue their charitable censures of my weake or vndigested instructions, which I no way meane to them, but to babes in Surgery, and so I conclude to the honour of the Almighty, concerning the Scuruy for this time.

Concerning the Fluxes of the bellie.

THe principall Fluxes of the belly by a common consent of diuers ancient writers, are chiefly referred to three kinds, namely:

{ *Leienteria.*
 { *Diarrhaea.*
 { *Disenteria.*

What Leienteria is.

The causes of Leienteria.

Cruditie a cause.

Leienteria is distinguished to be that Fluxe which either passeth the sustenance taken, wholly vndigested, and that without any bloud at all, and without great paine, or as it were halfe digested. The true causes of *Leienteria* proceede chiefly through imbecility and weakenesse of the stomake, which may be occasioned many waies, whereby the vertue retentive is weakened; yea and sometimes the stomake referuing apostumation is either wholly weakened, and cold and broken, or sometimes by crude humidities is oppressed, and must be strengthened, both inwardly and outwardly, by things that corroborate and warme the same, as is sirupe *de absinthio*, or *oleum absinthij*, Chymice

The Table.

<p>Putrificare, Putrefaction,</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 2em;">Q</p> <p>Quartations, Quicksilver his different operations, 194. vide Mercurie. Quils for stitching, Quinta { Essentia, Essentia vini,</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 2em;">R</p> <p>Radix { Althea, Angelica, China, Consolida, Pirethrum, Raphanus siluestris,</p> <p>Rasion, A Razor, Rauens bills, Realger, Reductio, Repurgation, Resina, Resolution; Restinction, A Restrictiue, Retortum, Reuerberation, Rhabarbarum, Rob { Berberum, Citoniorum, } Rosa solis, Rosarubra, Rosemarie, Rosemary water.</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 2em;">S</p> <p>Sabina,</p>	<p>324 324.346 346 27.37 324.346 325 121 122 97 122 121.122 122 346 3 11 325 346 347 108 347 347 162 325 325.347 94 81 55 116 119 56 121</p>	<p>Saccharum, Absinthij, Alkali Amoniacus Colcotharis, Communis, Gemme, Nitri, Petra, Tartari, Salt, the antiquity, What Salt is good in meates, Salts necessity and utility, Salts temperature, Salts healing vertues, Salts praise, Salvia, Saluatorie, Sarsaperilla, Sassaphras water, Saturnus, A Saw for dismembring, Sawe for the head, Scammonium, Scuruie what it is, it, 179. the signes, cure, 183. 184. 185. 186. 187. 188 189. 190. 191. the cure by lotions, 191. 192. 193. by oyles, 193. by unguents, 193. 194. 196. the cure for the vlcers of the Scuruie, 197 198. 199. 200. 201. Searces, Section, Segregation, X x</p>	<p>102 69.286 526 325 69.272.325 69.195.286.287.289 275.326 326 250. the kindes, 271 272 272.273 274.275 275.276 288. 289. 290. 291 307 119 24.25 97.98 56 312 7 7 94 178. the names of 181. 182. the 183. 184. 185. 186. 187. 188 189. 190. 191. the cure by lotions, 191. 192. 193. by oyles, 193. by 193. 194. 196. the cure 197 198. 199. 200. 201. 37 347 347 Anethi</p>
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